

Advancement in Studies on Effects of Sexual Harassment: A Bibliometric Analysis

Vandana Dangwal¹ & Uma Bahuguna²

1. Research Scholar, Department of Sociology and Social Work, Hemvati Nandan Bahuguna Garhwal University, Srinagar Garhwal, Uttarakhand, India Email: vandanadangwal55@gmail.com (* Correspondence Author).
2. Associate Professor, Department of Sociology and Social Work, Hemvati Nandan Bahuguna Garhwal University, Srinagar Garhwal, Uttarakhand, India Email: umabahuguna01@gmail.com

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Abstract

Sexual harassment is a widespread social phenomenon that negatively influences individuals' potential. Even after ages of human progression and a rise in academicians highlighting the issue of harassment, post-1982, it remains a global concern. Indeed, the advent of the me-too movement and ever-increasing news of harassment calls for urgent attention of the research fraternity to study the relative expansion and trends of harassment. Henceforth, to address the effects of harassment, this study attempts to undertake a bibliometric analysis using data extraction from the Scopus database for the period 1982 to 2023. The same has been mapped by using Vos Viewer software. The study further provides an overview of published and cited data for the critical studies, authors, journals, organizations, and countries. It also highlights a collaborative network between various authors and countries, keyword co-occurrences, and the chronology of comparative developments.

Keywords: Bibliometric analysis, Scopus, Sexual harassment, Vos-Viewer.

Introduction

Ever since the research on sexual harassment started, the research fraternity has deliberately covered various related topics of sexual harassment as well. One such theme under sexual harassment is the 'Effect of Sexual Harassment.' Studies have used both terms "effect" and "impact" to convey the same and, thus, often used interchangeably. Therefore, from this point on, the term "effect" will be used in this article. Sexual harassment is unwanted contact carrying sexual connotations without consent; unwanted sexual approaches, requesting sexual favors, and making sexual comments or gestures anywhere are all considered forms of sexual harassment (Mitchell, Ybarra, and Korchmaros 2014). Even though harassment can happen to everyone, studies have shown that compared to other demographic groups, harassment of women and members of underrepresented communities—including persons of color and LGBTQ+ occurs more frequently (Radde, 2018). Lesbians and gay men claim that since they defy accepted gender stereotypes, they are targeted sexually (Konik & Cortina, 2008). In addition to gender-based harassment, racist harassment is common in many nations, and women of color have reported racial harassment (Golden, 2019; Woods et al., 2009). Sexual harassment motivated by race also negatively impacts the victims (Buchanan & Fitzgerald, 2008). Women often believe inter-racial harassment to be more detrimental than intra-racial harassment (Woods et al., 2009) and often link Post-traumatic stress disorder to racial sexual harassment (Buchanan et al., 2018).

Studies about the effect of sexual harassment have documented harassment attributes from various socio-economic and occupational backgrounds, such as educational institutions, workplaces, flight

attendants, medicine, the hospitality sector, politics, sports, military and others (Bell et al., 2018; Hill & Silva, 2005; Norman et al., 2013; Samir et al., 2012; Sang et al., 2016; Stark & Meschik, 2018). According to the global supply chain survey, 85% of female employees were concerned about sexual harassment. Substantial impacts have also been noted on both occupational and health fronts (Fitzgerald & Cortina, 2018; Kaplan, 1991; Shaw et al., 2018). Increased incompetence and lack of concentration in work and education, change in institutions, organizations, or career lines, or overall withdrawal from a career are some ramifications of harassment (Bondestam & Lundqvist, 2020; McLaughlin et al., 2017; Vargas et al., 2020). Harassment even forces individuals to withdraw or alter their access to day-to-day facilities, such as public transport (Quinones, 2020), public places (Bowman, 1993), digital devices, and digital space (Winkelman et al., 2015; Worsley et al., 2017). On psychophysical fronts, headache, nausea, sleep disturbance, change in eating habits, menstrual disturbances, obesity, posttraumatic stress disorder, etc., was also communicated by studies (Ho et al., 2012; Sivertsen et al., 2019; Van Tu et al., 2020; Wood et al., 2021). The negative effects of harassment are also associated with substance abuse. Wilchek-Aviad and Oren (2022) argue that few victims tried to reduce the impact of sexual harassment by exploiting cannabis and hard drugs. Thus, various studies have propounded adverse and diverse effects of sexual harassment. Further, the advent of the MeToo movement using the hashtag Me Too also drew attention in 2017 (Fileborn & Loney-Howes, 2019). MeToo voices have become prominent in many industries, including higher education (Dey & Mendes, 2022), entertainment (Tally, 2021), medicine (Holroyd-Leduc & Straus, 2018), tourism (Ram, 2021), hospitality (Pearlman and Bordelon 2022), politics (Castle et al., 2020) and others (Cavico & Mujtaba, 2021; Fortado, 2018; Heminway, 2019). Moreover, the PhD students also used the hashtag #MeTooPhD to share their harassment experience (Hardy K, 2018). Thus, the widespread nature and ever-increasing news of harassment calls for urgent attention of the research fraternity to study the relative expansion and trends of sexual harassment.

Rationale of the Study

Despite the ills of harassment, the existing literature on the same is limited. Henceforth, this study attempts to delve into the effects of harassment by conducting a bibliometric analysis for the period 1977 to 2022 by using a Scopus database. The study further provides an overview of published and cited data for the critical studies, authors, journals, organizations, and countries. It also highlights a collaborative network between various authors and countries, keyword co-occurrences, and the chronology of comparative developments.

Database and Methodology

Methodology

A. Selection of Database and Data Extraction

The objective of the current study is to review the body of literature on the subject of sexual harassment to determine the most important works for comprehending contemporary developments in the field. We searched the most frequently accessed databases used by researchers to locate reliable documents on the topic. Scopus was taken into account in that inquiry. The Scopus database contains thousands of scholarly publications and details about their authors, affiliations, and citations. Studies published in the Core Collection of the Scopus database between 1982 and 2023 were used for the bibliometric analysis since the database of this collection includes citations, affiliations, and highly scientific studies. The search was done by February 2024 and was delimited to articles published in the English language only. In the current study, we present our target as 'Database' = Scopus Core Collection and enter a retrieval formula of 'TS' = 'sexual harassment' AND 'effect' OR 'impact' into the advanced search field with the time span of 1982–2023. The document search was run within the title, keywords, or abstract fields of the articles related to the effect or impact of sexual harassment. Accordingly, 2,158 documents were retrieved initially; the first two documents appeared in the 'Work and Occupations' and 'American Journal of Orthopsychiatry' in 1982. We then refined the items based on the English language, limiting them to 2087 documents (see Figure 1). We included 1,842 documents after the refinement of document types by including only articles and reviews published in journals.

B. Codification Process

The identified research articles were filtered and exported via a Comma Separated Value (CSV) file. The CSV file comprised of a list of Author(s), Author(s) ID, Document title, Electronic Identification (EID), Source title, volume, issue, pages, Citation count, Source and document type, publication stage, DOI, Open Access, Affiliation, Serial Identifier (ISSN), PubMed ID, Publisher, Editor (s), the language of the original document, correspondence address, abbreviated source title, Abstract, Authors keyword, Index keyword, Funding Detail with Number, Acronym, Synonym, funding text, conference information, and references.

A. Indicators

Based on Castillo-Vergara, Alvarez-Marin, and Placencio-Hidalgo (2018), this study has utilized the quantity, quality, and structural indicators. The quantity indicator reflects productivity by measuring the number of publications, whereas the quality indicator estimates effectiveness by measuring the citation count of authors and publications. Further, the structural indicator determines the relationship between authors and countries.

D. Data Analysis Tools

This study used the VOS viewer version 1.6.18. It is a software program used for creating and visualizing bibliometric maps. It helps to examine and analyze the relationship between document citations, authors, countries, journals, and organizations. VOS viewer has an advantage over other software for bibliometric mapping as it can illustrate a graphical representation of maps (Qiu et al., 2017).

Significance of Bibliometric analysis

Bibliometric analysis tends to identify and analyze massive datasets to understand the spread of extensive scientific knowledge and its evolution (Donthu et al., 2021). It uses macroscopic exploration to understand a large set of academic literature (van Nunen et al., 2018) and probes into research work patterns, the relation among authors, journals, institutions, and countries and tries to identify and quantify research patterns between them (W. Li & Zhao, 2015). Bibliometrics directs researchers about the latest advances, research directions, and leading topics in a particular field of research (Wang et al., 2014). It also provides for the latent identification of both content-wise and geographical current gaps in research disciplines (Gall et al., 2015).

The program provides the tools to interpret massive visualization networks (van Eck & Waltman, 2014). Labels and circles present the items in the visualization network. As a result, the approximate relationship between each item in the visualization network is indicated by the distance between them. In general, the stronger the relationship between two items, the closer they appear to one another. Lines that stand in for links connect the network's parts. The cluster to which an item belongs in the cluster network determines the intelligent local moving algorithm and the item's color.

An Overview of Research on "Effect of Sexual Harassment"

The initial two publications on the 'Effect of Sexual Harassment' discovered in Scopus, titled 'Blue Collar Blues: The Sexual Harassment of Autoworkers' by Gruber and Bjorn and 'Stress Effect of Sexual Harassment on the Job' by P. Crull, were published in 1982, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1.
Research Trend on the
Effect of Sexual Harassment
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Most Relevant Research Articles on the Effect of Sexual Harassment

Table 1: Top ten articles based on total citation.

Rank	Title	Authors	Publications	Total Citation
1	Controlling other People: the impact of power on stereotyping	Fiske (1993)	American Psychologist	1352
2	LGB and questioning students in school: The moderating effects of homophobic bullying and school climate on negative outcome	Birkett (2009)	Journal of youth and adolescence	559
3	Interpersonal mistreatment in the workplace: the interface and impact of general incivility and sexual harassment	Lim (2005)	Journal of applied psychology	442
4	Perceived impacts of tourism: the case of samos	Haralambopoulos (1996)	Annals of tourism research	418
5	X-rated: Sexual attitudes and behaviours/ associated with U.S. early adolescents' exposure to sexually explicit media	Brown (2009)	Communication Research	408
6	Job-related and psychological effects of sexual harassment in the workplace: Empirical evidence from two organizations	Schneider (1997)	Journal of Applied Psychology	369
7	Who women are, who women should be: Descriptive and Prescriptive Gender Stereotyping in Sex Discrimination	Burgess (1999)	Psychology, Public Policy, and Law	354
8	Prevalence of workplace violence against healthcare worker: a systematic review and meta-analysis	Liu (2019)	Occupational and Environmental medicine	334
9	A New generation of women veterans: Stressors faced by women deploy to Iraq and Afghanistan	Street (2009)	Clinical Psychology Review	327
10	School Climate for transgender youth: a mixed method investigation of students' experiences and school responses	McGuire (2010)	Journal of Youth and Adolescence	318

Source: Authors' analysis.

The most significant paper found during the analysis was "Controlling Other People: The Impact of Power on Stereotyping," published by an American psychologist in 1993. It has around 1352 citations (Table 1). The research domain that is covered by these ten top publications is broad and includes topics like sexual harassment and abuse in the workplace, sexual harassment at work, sexual harassment at school, sexual attitudes and behaviors, and other effects of sexual harassment on the mind and body.

Publications by Journal

From the Scopus database, 976 journals with 1,841 publications published on the topic were found. Based on the number of documents published, Figure 5 illustrates the top 10 journals in the discipline. Together, these ten journals published 256 articles, or 13.9% of the sample total. With 62 papers published, the Journal of Interpersonal Violence has the most, accounting for 3.36% of the sample. Sex Roles ranks second with 58 published papers, or 3.15% of the sample overall. With 24 articles, Psychology of Women Quarterly holds the third place. Furthermore, (refer to Figure 2), research on this subject may be published in journals across a variety of disciplines, including social science, medicine, psychology, business, accounting and management, arts and humanities, and Nursing among others.

Table 2 represents the top 10 journals with the most documents published during 1982-2023. Figure 6 depicts the relationship between sources/journals and citations in the field of Effect of Sexual Harassment research, and only journals with at least 10 published papers were considered for analysis. The association between sources and citations denotes where an author chooses to publish their article.

Figure 2. Top ten research directions in the field of the Effect of Sexual Harassment

Table 2: Top ten sources based on number of publications

Rank	Source	Publisher	Documents	Citation	Citation per document	Total Link Strength
1	Journal of Interpersonal Violence	Sage	62	1099	17.72	54
2	Sex Roles	Springer	58	2618	45.13	128
3	Psychology of Women Quarterly	Sage	24	1589	66.20	97
4	International Journal of Environmental Research And Public Health	MDPI	21	218	10.38	12
5	Journal of Applied Social Psychology	Wiley Online Library	17	505	29.70	45
6	Plos One	PLOS	17	153	9	8

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7	Employee Responsibilities And Rights Journal	Springer	15	140	9.33	19
8	Violence Against Women	Sage	15	835	55.66	35
9	Violence Against Victims	Springer	14	686	49	16
10	Child Abuse and Neglect	Elsevier	13	614	47.23	7

Source: Authors' analysis.

Figure 3. Density Visualisation map based on publication volume of journals

Analysis of Publications by Countries

Table 3: Top ten countries based on number of documents.

Rank	Countries	Documents	Percent	Citation	per document	Total Strength	Link
1	United States	951	51.65	34024	35.777	887	
2	United Kingdom	159	8.63	3805	23.93	312	
3	Australia	130	7.06	4107	31.59	378	
4	Canada	118	6.40	4006	33.94	225	
5	Germany	54	2.93	1028	19.03	154	
6	China	46	2.49	1315	28.58	258	
7	Sweden	44	2.39	999	22.70	73	
8	India	37	2.00	454	12.27	34	
9	Netherlands	33	1.79	807	24.45	90	
10	South Korea	32	1.73	246	7.68	70	

Source: Authors' analysis.

Figure 4. Network Visualisation map of countries based on publication volume

In total, 1841 papers on the effects of sexual harassment were published by 164 different countries. Data on the distribution of publications by nation are displayed in Table 2. According to a review of the literature, the United States contributes the most (951 publications), followed by the United Kingdom (159), Australia (130), and Canada (118). The data as mentioned earlier is shown in Table 2. Based on bibliometric analysis, these countries publish a large number of research publications, making them the top contributors to the literature on the effects of sexual harassment. These nations may have benefited from funding and demand opportunities, which has led to the growth of this field of study. The data indicates that, with the most citations, the United States seems to have a distinct advantage in this field of study, followed by Australia and Canada. At 35.77 average citations per document, the US leads the world in this category as well. The average number of citations for Australia, Canada, and the United Kingdom is 31.59, 33.94, and 23.93, respectively. India is ranked eighth in the world for publications, with just 37 articles and an average citation rate of 12.27 per article, according to the literature.

Analysis of Publications by Organizations

Table 4: Classification of publications by Organizations.

Rank	Organizations	Documents	Citation	Citation per document
1	University of Illinois Urbana Champaign	35	3402	97.2
2	VA Medical Centre	33	1308	39.63
3	University of Michigan, Ann Arbor	30	2137	71.23
4	University of Toronto	27	1172	43.40
5	University of Illinois at Chicago	23	882	38.34
6	University of Michigan Medical School	22	1928	87.63
7	Boston University Chobanian & Avedisian School of Medicine	20	909	45.45
8	University of Kentucky	20	838	41.9
9	University of Nebraska-Lincoln	20	312	15.6
10	Stanford University	18	511	28.38

Source: Authors' analysis.

The major organizations that published papers on the Effect of Sexual Harassment are illustrated on the map produced by the VOSviewer program (refer to Figure 7). This information leads us to the conclusion that the top five institutions publishing articles in this field of study are the University of

Illinois at Chicago, University of Michigan, Ann Arbor, University of Toronto, and University of Illinois Urbana Champaign.

Figure 5. Network visualization map organisations based on number of publications

Table 3 shows the topmost organizations that have published at least 18 documents in the Effect of sexual harassment research field. From the data in Table 3, we can see that 9 organizations have published at least 20 papers in the Effect of Sexual Harassment field during 1982–2023. It is noteworthy that the University of Illinois Urbana Champaign from the USA is in first position with the highest number of publications (35) in this research field. All top ten universities belong to the USA.

It was discovered the University of Illinois Urbana Champaign had published 51 documents that received the highest number of citations (3402). The average number of citations per document was discovered to be 97.2, which was the highest (see Table 3). University of Michigan Medical School reported the second-highest average citation per document (87.63).

Authors and Co-authors Relationship

‘Co-authorship assesses the most productive set of documents, as well as those with the greatest number of joint publications’ (Martínez-López et al., 2018). The authors who work together on the research on the effects of sexual harassment are displayed in the author co-authorship map.

The most influential researchers in the field were identified using citation metrics and the authors' total number of published publications. 98 writers out of the 5577 have produced at least three publications. A network of co-authors and authors based on the effects of sexual harassment is illustrated in Figure 8. Rospenda has published 17 publications on the effects of sexual harassment among them. Cortina L.M., Magley V., Fineran S., Pina A., Gruber J., and Street A. are his closest collaborators. There are 22 total link strength (TLS). According to Table 4, Rospenda, K.M. is the most well-known and prolific author in the field, having published the most (17 publications), followed by Richman, J.A. (15) and Fitzgerald, L.F. (16). Fitzgerald, however, had the most citation (1970), followed by Drasgow (1069) and Cortina (1864).

The average number of citations Cortina received per document was 143.38, with Fitzgerald, L.F. (123.12) and Espelage, D.L. (99.125) coming in second and third, respectively. Academics view authors with a higher number of citations as more influential. A high-quality document is indicated by the average number of citations per document. The analysis leads to the conclusion that, in comparison to the other documents, the ones from Fitzgerald, Cortina, Drasgow, Espelage, D.L., and Rospenda, K.M. had a greater impact and influence (see Table 5).

Discussion

The present study conducted a bibliometric analysis using the VOS viewer tool, examining several facets of published papers such as the contributions of authors, documents, countries, and organizations to the subject. The following findings from the bibliometric study of the Effect of Sexual Harassment studies were obtained: First, a collection of papers with the Effect of Sexual Harassment research have been published in several multidisciplinary domains, notably Social Sciences, Medicine, Psychology, Business management & accounting, arts & humanities, nursing, agricultural & biological sciences, environmental science, neuroscience, and economic, econometrics & finance. With papers appearing in a range of fields, it is evident that the Effect of Sexual Harassment research has become a prominent area of study.

The first two papers in Scopus on the Effect of Sexual Harassment were found in 1982 and were written by Gruber and Bjorn, and P. Crull in *Work and Occupations* and *American Journal of Orthopsychiatry*, respectively. Since then, there have been a great deal more publications, and as indicated by a rise in citations, these works have grown in importance over time. The research literature on the Effect of Sexual Harassment is dispersed among a sizable number of journals from several fields, as the publication tendency analysis reveals. The Effect of Sexual Harassment is a broad field that encompasses several academic fields. With 62 publications published, the *Journal of Interpersonal Violence* has the most, accounting for 3.36 % of the sample as a whole. Out of 164 countries, the top 10 countries have 1604 documents which is 87.07 percent of the total. The United States is the most prolific provider with 951 publications, followed by the United Kingdom, and Australia according to bibliometric data. Based on the number of research publications produced, Scopus determines that these are the nations/regions that make the biggest contributions to the EO-performance literature. University of Illinois Urbana Champaign, VA Medical Centre, University of Michigan, Ann Arbor, University of Toronto, and University of Illinois at Chicago are among the top five institutions publishing articles in this research domain.

Conclusion

The current study successfully attempts to evaluate the research performance in the field of the effect of sexual harassment concerning bibliometric analysis and network visualization carried out with the aid of the VOS viewer tool. The study summarizes the research on the Effects of Sexual Harassment in the last 41 years based on the Scopus dataset. According to the findings, research in the relevant field has gained pace in the past five years. Since the effect of sexual harassment is a sub-theme of sexual harassment, the studies under consideration are also limited; therefore, the number of collaborations among researchers, countries, and organizations is also limited. Collaborations between authors Fitzgerald, Cortina, and Glasgow have been notable in the maps. Similarly, in the United States, little domestic cooperation with few research links is observed among organizations. It is clear that, in addition to old spaces like the workplace and educational campuses, harassment has infiltrated new ventures like social media and digital space, multiplying its threats and impacts dynamically. Diverse representation and the prevalence of harassment have drawn researchers' attention, resulting in a mushrooming growth in the number of documents and citations in the last five years. In the coming years, the upward trend is anticipated to persist. Every methodology in research has its own set of limitations, and bibliometrics is no exception. The data for this study were retrieved from the Scopus bibliographic database only, so future research may be conducted using documents from global databases such as Web of Science, and Google Scholar to provide a broad and more complete picture of the growth of the discipline of the effects of sexual harassment. However, this study attempted to thoroughly assess the literature on the effects of sexual harassment by addressing multiple dimensions and fostering collaboration among various stakeholders in the research fraternity.

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